

Performance modelling of an ammonia-water absorption-compression heat pump for steam generation in food processing

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ABSTRACT

At the present time, fossil fuel is still the primary energy source for steam production in food processing. To mitigate climate change and promote sustainable development, there is an urgent need for eco-friendly steam boilers. The absorption-compression heat pumps (ACHP) using an ammonia-water mixture as the working fluid can provide high heat sink temperature up to 140°C at low discharge pressure levels and with temperature glides in absorption and desorption processes. The present study investigated the performance of the ACHP for hot water and steam production. The simulation model was established based on the ACHP prototype in the NTNU lab. A case of 150 kW heating capacity was simulated with a high pressure of 23.65 bar and a low pressure of 4 bar. The ACHP system COP was 2.85 for a pressurized hot water supply temperature of 105 °C. The effects of heat sink outlet temperature and part-load and overload conditions on the system performance were investigated.

Keywords: High-temperature Heat Pump, Steam Production, Ammonia-water Mixture, Absorption-compression, Energy Efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

Steam (water vapor) is one of the most important processing media in food processing because it is clean, nontoxic, and with high latent heat. Steam serves various purposes in the food sector such as sterilization, drying, cooking, and cleaning. At the present time, fossil fuel is still the primary energy source for steam production, which is nearly one-third of the total energy consumption in the food industry. To mitigate climate change and promote sustainable development, there is an urgent need for eco-friendly steam boilers.

High-temperature heat pumps (HTHPs) using natural refrigerants as working fluid have gained particular interest for steam boilers replacement in recent years due to their low global warming potential (GWP) and well-known environmental impacts (Mateu-Royo et al., 2021). The HTHPs were found to be competitive for steam boilers replacement in supplying heat of up to 180 °C with temperature lifts of up to 160 K (Bergamini et al., 2019). The major limitations of employing HTHPs for high-temperature heat supply are the critical point of the refrigerants and the compressor operating constraints at high-temperature levels and pressures (Ommen et al., 2015). Utilizing the wet compression by a liquid-injected screw compressor is a potential solution for the high-temperature applications of compressors (Zaytsev, 2003).

The absorption-compression heat pumps (ACHP) using an ammonia-water mixture as the working fluid can provide high heat sink temperatures up to 140 °C at low discharge pressure levels and with temperature glides in absorption and desorption processes employing commercially available components. Compared with applying gas boilers, ACHPs are more economical (Jensen et al., 2015). Using an oil-free twin-screw compressor with liquid injection, the compressor discharge temperature and compression power can be decreased (Ahrens et al., 2023), which might ensure the safe operation of the ACHP with a high heat supply temperature and a high energy efficiency.

The present study aims to investigate the performance of an existing ACHP for hot water and steam production. The simulation model was established based on the ACHP prototype in the NTNU lab. An oil-

free compressor with liquid injection is used for the ACHP prototype. A case of 150 kW heating capacity was simulated with a high pressure of 23.65 bar and a low pressure of 4 bar. The performance of the ACHP at off-design conditions was investigated. The effects of sink outlet temperatures and sink fluid mass flow rates on the system performance were analysed. The system performance at part-load and overload conditions are investigated.

2. METHOD

In the present study, a numerical model of the ACHP was developed based on the ACHP prototype in the NTNU lab using the Dymola modelling platform with Modelica language. The performance of the ACHP at different operating conditions was investigated. The details are described in this section.

2.1. The ACHP process description

A principle sketch of the ACHP steam generation system is illustrated in Figure 1. The ACHP using ammonia and water mixture as the working fluid was designed based on the Osenbrück cycle (Osenbrück, 1895) as a vapor compression cycle with an additional liquid circuit.

Figure 1: A principle sketch of the ACHP steam generation system

The cycle consists of a compressor, an absorber, a desorber, an internal heat exchanger (IHX), an expansion valve, a solution pump, and a liquid-vapor separator. Low-grade heat from the heat source is transferred to the refrigerant in the desorber. Vapor containing the predominantly low boiling component of the working fluid mixture is generated in the desorber at a non-constant temperature glide. At the outlet of the desorber, the working fluid is a liquid-vapor two-phase mixture. The liquid and vapor phases are separated in the liquid-vapor separator to make sure only the vapor enters the compressor. The lean solution from the bottom of the separator is pressurized by the solution pump to the high pressure and then heated by the rich solution in the IHX. The vapor is compressed to the high pressure with a high discharge temperature by the compressor. To achieve a high temperature-lift and high sink outlet temperature, the compressor is working at the oil-free condition and the high-pressure lean solution downstream the solution pump is injected into the compressor for lubrication and cooling. The

vapor and lean solution are mixed in a mixer to obtain an ammonia-water mixture in an equilibrium state before entering the absorber. The ammonia is absorbed into the lean solution inside the absorber and heat is released to the heat sink. The resulting rich ammonia solution leaving the absorber goes into the IHX and is subcooled by the lean solution. Then the rich solution is throttled to the low pressure by the expansion valve resulting in a liquid-vapor mixture which is fed to the desorber.

Pressurized water is used as the heat sink. In the absorber, the temperature of the sink water can be increased to 100-150°C. The hot pressurized water from the sink outlet then will be supplied to hot water users in different food processes. For steam users, the hot pressurized water is flashed in a flash tank by a throttle valve and then is supplied to different processes by a steam compressor.

2.2. The ACHP experimental test facility

To investigate the performance of the ACHP steam generation system and each component, an experimental prototype of the ACHP named “Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump” was established in a NTNU lab based on the basic ACHP cycle illustrated in Figure 1 but without the steam generation loop, as shown in Figure 2. The system was designed for a maximum heat capacity of 200 kW with a maximum operating pressure of 40 bar and an operational temperature ranging from -10 °C to 190 °C. The test facility consists of an absorption-compression heat pump system and an auxiliary system which provides the required heat source and heat sink water circuits.

Figure 2: The ACHP prototype in the NTNU lab

2.3. Thermodynamic modelling of the ACHP system

The performance modelling of an ACHP was conducted by Dymola (Dynamic Modelling Library, version 2022, Dassault systems) (Systèmes, 2022) using Modelica language. Two commercial Modelica libraries were utilized for the simulations, namely TIL-suite 3.10.0 and TILMedia 3.10.0 which are provided by TLK-Thermo GmbH. The ACHP system model and component models were all built based on the “Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump” prototype in the NTNU lab. A simplified simulation model of the ACHP is illustrated in Figure 3.

To simplify the simulation, the pressure drops caused by friction in the system and heat losses to the surroundings were neglected. The mixing of the weak solution and vapor at the absorber inlet was assumed

pressure (p_{HP}) as $p_{int} = \sqrt{p_{LP} \cdot p_{HP}}$. The isentropic efficiency and volumetric efficiency of the compressor used in the simulation were both 0.7. The speed of the low-pressure compressor was controlled by the intermediate pressure and the speed of the high pressure compressor was controlled by the desired heat sink outlet temperature by PI controllers. The intercooler was modelled by a tube heat exchanger with a heat boundary which can provide a constant cooling load.

2.3.2. Heat exchangers

All heat exchangers used for the ACHP prototype are plate heat exchangers manufactured by Alfa Laval AS. The plate dimensions of the heat exchangers are listed in Table 1. In all the heat exchangers, the fluids on different sides of the plates flow counter-currently to enhance the heat transfer. Because there is no appropriate correlation for absorption and desorption found in literatures, the heat transfer was calculated by different correlations for approximation, as listed in Table 2. Constant heat transfer coefficients were used in the simulation. The pressure drops inside the heat exchangers were neglected to simplify the model and reduce the computation cost.

Table 1. Plate dimensions of the heat exchangers

	Desorber	Absorber	IHX
Number of plates	40	40	20
Length (m)	0.9	0.9	0.25
Width (m)	0.111	0.111	0.111
Corrugation angle (°)	50	65	65
Wall thickness (m)	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004
Pattern Amplitude (m)	0.002	0.002	0.002
Pattern wave length (m)	0.007	0.007	0.007

Table 2. Heat transfer coefficient correlations applied to the heat exchangers

	Water	Refrigerant
Desorber	Martin (1996)	Taboas et al. (2012) with Martin (1996) for liquid phase heat transfer
Absorber	Martin (1996)	Bell (1972) with Martin (1996) for vapor phase heat transfer and Yan et al. (1999) for liquid phase heat transfer
	Rich solution	Lean solution
IHX	Martin (1996)	Martin (1996)

2.3.3. Separator and receiver

The liquid-vapor separator prevents the vapor phase entering the compressor and vapor phase entering the solution pump. It serves as a buffer tank in the ACHP prototype system. The volume of the separator is 196 l. In the simulation, the real volume of the separator was used and the filling level was set at 50%.

In the ACHP prototype system, a high-pressure receiver is placed downstream the absorber and upstream the IHX to ensure that only liquid phase rich solution enters the IHX to obtain a high heat transfer rate. By controlling the liquid level in the receiver, the operating condition of the ACHP can also be adjusted. Because the high-pressure receiver has zero contribution to the thermodynamic part of the system, it was neglected in the simulation due to the lack of a proper model in TIL library.

2.3.4. Solution pump and expansion valve

In the simulation, the solution pump was operated at a constant mass flow rate which was determined by the circulation ratio. The pump efficiency was assumed to be 0.4. The expansion process was assumed to be isenthalpic and at the outlet of the expansion valve, the liquid-vapor two phase flow was at thermodynamic

equilibrium state. The opening area of the exposition valve was adjusted to control the low pressure of the heat pump by a PI controller.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate the performance of the ACHP prototype “Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump” in NTNU lab for hot water and steam production, a case of 150 kW heating capacity was simulated. The operating parameters are listed in Table 3. The heat sink fluid is pressurized water which can be used as supply water for the steam generation system, as shown in Figure 1.

Table 3. Operating parameters applied to simulation

Source inlet temperature	70 °C
Sink inlet temperature	75 °C
Low pressure	4 bar
High pressure	23.65 bar
Intermediate pressure	9.7 bar
Rich solution mass fraction	0.6
Circulation ratio	0.59

3.1. System performance

The simulation results are illustrated in Table 4. The state point number of streams is according to Figure 3. At the low pressure of 4 bar, the vapor quality at the outlet of the desorber is 0.41 and the lean solution circulation ratio is 0.59. At the high pressure of 23.65 bar, the obtained sink outlet temperature is 105 °C and the compressor frequency is 33 Hz. The compressor intercooling load was determined by injecting the high-pressure lean solution (stream no.10, downstream the solution pump and upstream the IHX) with 15 % of the compressor’s suction mass flow rate. With the intercooling, the compressor discharge temperature is decreased from 276 °C to 160.3 °C and the COP of the ACHP is increased from 2.14 to 2.85.

Table 4. Simulation results of the ACHP system

i^{th} stream	Mass flow rate (kg/s)	Ammonia mass fraction (-)	Temperature (°C)	Pressure (bar)
1	0.1183	0.975	57.7	4
2	0.1183	0.975	157.3	9.7
3	0.1183	0.975	160.3	23.65
4	0.2887	0.6	118.5	23.65
5	0.2887	0.6	88.5	23.65
6	0.2887	0.6	84	23.65
7	0.2887	0.6	30	4
8	0.2887	0.6	57.7	4
9	0.1703	0.35	57.7	4
10	0.1703	0.35	61.1	23.65
11	0.1703	0.35	81.2	23.65
12	0.1183	0.975	72.7	9.7
13	1.2	-	70	5
14	1.2	-	44.95	5
15	1.2	-	75	10
16	1.2	-	105	10

3.2. Effects of the sink outlet temperature

The effect of the sink outlet temperature on the system performance is illustrated in Figure 4. The same heat sink and source inlet temperatures were used for all the simulations. With the increase of the sink outlet temperature and system temperature lift, the heat capacity is increased and the system COP is decreased. Figure 5 shows the compressor discharge pressures and temperatures at different sink outlet temperatures. With the increase of the heat load to the heat sink side, the required pressure in absorber and the consequent compressor discharge temperature are also increased. This is because more heat is required to be provided by the compressor and higher refrigerant mass flow rates are needed for the heat transportation.

Figure 4: COPs and heat capacities at different heat sink outlet temperatures

Figure 5: Discharge pressures and temperatures at different heat sink outlet temperatures

As shown in Figure 4-5, when the heat sink outlet temperature is increased from 100 °C to 105 °C, the required pressure in the absorber increases 4 % and the system COP is decreased by 5 %. When the heat sink outlet temperature is increased from 110 °C to 115 °C, the required absorption pressure increases 11 % and the system COP is reduced by 17 %. With the increase of the heat sink outlet temperature, more power is needed to be supplied by the vapor compression, which reduces the system performance. At a high sink supply temperature of 120 °C and a temperature lift of 50 K, the ACHP still can achieve a COP of 1.83. Further increasing the sink outlet temperature will significantly reduce the heat pump performance. For most

cases in the food industry, hot water temperature of 80 °C - 100°C and steam temperature of 105 °C are sufficient.

As shown in Figure 5, at the highest sink outlet temperature of 120 °C, the compressor discharge temperature is high up to 180 °C, which might damage the compressor bearings when the injection liquid is evaporated and there is not sufficient lubrication liquid for bearings. In the simulations, the compressor intercooling heat flow rates were determined by the injection of the high pressure lean solution with 15 % of the vapor mass flow rate. To ensure smooth operation of the ACHP, the compressor discharge temperature should be maintained within a safe level by adjusting the liquid injection mass flow rate. At high sink outlet temperatures or high heat load conditions, the injection mass flow rate should be higher than 15 % of the vapor mass flow rate.

3.3. Effects of the heat sink water mass flow rate

By varying the heat sink water mass flow rate, the heat load to the heat sink is changed. To investigate the performance of the ACHP at part-load and overload conditions, the ACHP cycle at 60% -110% of the design heat capacity (90 kW - 166 kW) was simulated. The sink outlet temperature was maintained at a constant value of 105 °C. The source inlet temperature and mass flow rate were kept unchanged as listed in Table 3 and Table 4. The low pressure was maintained at 4 bar. The results are illustrated in Figure 6-8.

Figure 6 illustrates the COPs and heat loads at different sink water mass flow rates. With the decrease of the heat sink water mass flow rate, the heat load is decreased and the performance of the ACHP is improved. As shown in Figure 7, with the decrease of the heat sink water mass flow rate, the required rich solution mass flow rate is decreased, and the compressor discharge pressure is slightly decreased too. When the heat load decreases from 110 % to 60 % of the design point, the COP increases 19.3 %, the rich solution mass flow rate decreases 55.8 %, and the discharge pressure decreases 7 %. When the heat load is reduced, less heat is needed to be transported by the refrigerant, so the rich solution mass flow rate decreases at the same range as the sink water mass flow rate (50 %). The pressure in the absorber mainly depends on the sink outlet temperature which is constant at different heat loads so that the discharge pressure is not decreased much by the decreasing heat load. The slight decrease of the discharge pressure is mainly resulted by the over-dimensioned heat exchangers at lower heat loads when the refrigerant mass flow rate is reduced.

Figure 8 shows the circulation ratios and lean solution mass fractions at different sink water mass flow rates. The source inlet temperature and source fluid mass flow rate are maintained at the same value at varying heat loads. When the heat load is decreased, the refrigerant temperature at the outlet of the desorber is increased due to the reduced refrigerant mass flow rate. This results in the increase of the vapor quality at the outlet of the desorber and the decrease of the circulation ratio and lean solution ammonia mass fraction. The lower circulation ratio further contributes to the reduction of the rich solution mass flow rate and the increase of the system performance.

Figure 6: COPs and heat loads at different heat sink water mass flow rates

Figure 7: Rich solution mass flow rates and compressor discharge pressures at different heat sink water mass flow rates

Figure 8: Circulation ratios and lean solution ammonia mass fractions at different sink water mass flow rates

4. CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, the performance of the ACHP using ammonia-water mixture as working fluid for hot water and steam production was investigated numerically. The simulation model was established based on the ACHP prototype “Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump” in the NTNU lab. An oil-free compressor with liquid injection is used for the prototype. The lean solution is employed as the injection liquid for the lubrication, cooling and sealing of the compressor. A case of 150 kW heating capacity was simulated for a pressurized hot water supply temperature of 105 °C with a high pressure of 23.65 bar and low pressure of 4 bar. With the compressor intercooling, the discharge temperature is decreased from 276 °C to 160.3 °C and the COP of the ACHP is increased from 2.14 to 2.85. At a high sink supply temperature of 120 °C and a temperature lift of 50 K, the ACHP still can achieve a COP of 1.83. Further increasing the sink outlet temperature and system temperature lift will significantly reduce the heat pump performance. When the heat load of the heat pump is decreased from 110 % to 60 %, the COP increases 19.3 % and the discharge pressure decreases 7 %. To further investigate the characteristics and performance of the ACHP, the influences of pressure drops should be considered and variable heat transfer coefficients should be used for the heat exchangers. Experimental studies should be conducted to validate the simulation results.

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DATA AVAILABLE STATEMENT

The data supporting reported results can be found in a public repository under the following DIO: <https://doi.org/10.18710/4QOR04>.

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